

Enhancing Medical Image Processing and Analysis with Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract: Computer vision and image analysis rely heavily on machine learning. From structure-from-motion and object recognition to scene understanding and image segmentation and registration, there is a wide spectrum of problems. Information may be extracted from visual data using machine learning algorithms. A rapidly expanding area of deep learning is medical picture analysis. Standard machine learning (ML) methods from computer vision, ML models from deep learning, and medical image analysis are all examples of DL approaches and their uses in this area. Classifying things, such as lesions, into specific classes using input parameters like contrast and area obtained from segmented objects is one of the most recent uses of ml in computer-aided diagnosis and medical image analysis. An artificial neural network is conceptually based on a neural system. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and neural filters are at the heart of deep learning. Deep learning and other forms of ML that take images as input are highly effective and valuable technologies. In most cases, a medical specialist will be the one to make the interpretation of the medical data. Due to factors such as subjectivity, visual complexity, interpreter weariness, and large fluctuations, human specialists have a hard time interpreting images. Adding to deep learning's impressive track record of success in the real world, it has introduced novel, highly accurate solutions for medical imaging. For potential uses in healthcare in the future, it is considered a crucial technique.

Keywords: Neural Filters; Visual Data; Radiologists And Physicians; Ultrasound; X-Ray; Deep Learning; Magnetic Resonance; Computed Tomography; Computer-Assisted Interventions.

Introduction

Computerized tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MR), positron emission tomography (pet), ultrasound, x-ray, mammography, and other forms of medical imaging have been increasingly important in the last several decades for the early diagnosis, monitoring, and treatment of various disorders [9]. Clinicians, including radiologists and doctors, have traditionally been responsible for medical picture interpretation. Nevertheless, computer-assisted interventions have only lately started to help researchers and clinicians deal with the huge variances in pathology as well as the possible exhaustion of human specialists [10]. Even researchers and practitioners without a background in machine learning can make good use of deep learning in their work, particularly in fields like medical image analysis, thanks to advancements in machine learning models and techniques that have made the transition from human to computer-based analysis much simpler [11-15]. In order to diagnose a patient's illness,

medical imaging is essential. Deep learning techniques can process and analyse medical images, making it easier for doctors to diagnose patients when radiologists fail to do so for a variety of reasons, including (i) poor image resolution (in the spatial and spectral domains), (ii) high levels of noise and contrast, (iii) geometric deformations, and (iv) possible expert fatigue [16-22].

Machine learning is the focus of this paper. In machine learning, the algorithms used vary according to the needs of the paper. The majority of current intelligent methods for medical image processing advocate using several conventional machine learning classifiers [23-27]. This leads to the perennially contentious issue of "which machine learning classifier is the most successful and predictive in increasing the performance of medical image processing?" for the medical imaging industry [28]. Because of this, we are driven to make use of deep neural networks' immense potential in medical picture processing and analysis. The ability to examine interior anatomy in great detail without causing any harm is the primary advantage of medical image processing [29-35]. The creation and study of three-dimensional models of relevant anatomy can lead to better patient treatment outcomes, new medical equipment and medication delivery systems, and more precise diagnostics. Accurate digital recreation of biological features at various scales is made possible by the ever-improving imaging quality and powerful software tools. In both hard and soft tissues, its characteristics vary greatly [36-41]. More comprehensive understanding is possible through measurement, statistical analysis, and model building, for example, of the ways in which medical devices interact with patient anatomy.

Methodology

The goal of this paper is to improve medical photographs by applying deep neural network (dnn) image processing methods. There have been numerous applications of ML and AI techniques in healthcare, including medical image processing, computer-aided diagnosis, interpretation, fusion, registration, segmentation, image-guided therapy, analysis, retrieval, and computer-aided therapies. Methods from ml efficiently and effectively represent data by extracting it from photos. Machine learning and artificial intelligence help doctors make faster, more accurate diagnoses, as well as more precise predictions about the likelihood of diseases and how to prevent them. By using these methods, medical professionals and scientists will have a better grasp on how to examine the genetic differences that cause diseases. These methods incorporate both traditional, non-learning algorithms like support vector machines (SVMs), neural networks (NNs), and k-nearest neighbours (KNNs), as well as more advanced, learning algorithms like convolutional neural networks (CNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), long short-term memories (LSTMs), extreme learning models (ELMs), and generative adversarial networks (GANS). These algorithms make an effort to automatically learn various levels of representation, information, and abstraction from big sets of images that display the required data behaviour. Despite decades of impressive accuracy from automated disease identification using traditional medical imaging approaches, recent developments in machine learning have sparked a boom in deep learning.

Literature Review

To illustrate the difficulties of image interpretation, Mohamed et al. [1] employ image processing algorithms such k-means, roi-based segmentation, and watershed techniques. A variety of methods exist within the realm of picture processing that computers can employ. In order to facilitate easier diagnosis, segmentation attempts to divide the images into relevant parts. The ability to examine interior anatomy in great detail without causing any harm is the primary advantage of medical image processing. Creating and studying three-dimensional models of relevant anatomy can lead to better patient treatment outcomes, better medical device and drug delivery system development, and more accurate diagnosis. In recent years, it has emerged as a crucial instrument for the improvement of medicine. Pixels' histograms and threshold values are utilised in threshold segmentation. When the algorithms presented in this paper are unable to examine or cease images at their borders, image edge approaches are employed. Technical hurdles abound when dealing with medical image segmentation issues, such as boundaries that

are noisy or poorly defined. Low resolution (in the spatial and spectral domains), excessive levels of noise, low contrast, geometric deformations, and imaging artefacts are some of the common problems encountered during medical picture acquisition in most imaging modalities. Finer spatial sampling, made possible by a longer acquisition time, can help to prevent low contrast and poor resolution flaws.

Developing artificial neural networks and conducting a thorough examination of dla are presented by Puttagunta and Ravi [2]. This work offers intriguing medical imaging applications. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) and DLA, which provide promising medical imaging applications, are presented and analysed in this research. Digital mammography, X-rays, CT scans, and digital histopathology images are the main focus of most DLA implementations. It offers a comprehensive literature analysis on DLA-based medical picture categorization, detection, and segmentation. Accurate digital recreation of biological features at various scales is made possible by the ever-improving imaging quality and powerful software tools. Its characteristics vary greatly, spanning both hard and soft tissues. A more comprehensive understanding, for instance, of the interactions between medical equipment and patient anatomy, can be achieved by measurement, statistical analysis, and the development of simulation models that contain actual anatomical geometry. In order to handle real-world data without human labelling, deep learning is gradually transitioning to unsupervised and semi-supervised learning, but many existing dl implementations are supervised algorithms.

However, that would also make geometric modifications, such patient movement, more likely, which would lead to picture blurring. Medical image analysis is further complicated by imaging artefacts. The sheer volume of medical picture datasets is the primary issue. Image processing and visualisation algorithms need to be fine-tuned employing supercomputers equipped with graphics processing units and advanced parallelization techniques to handle the massive medical image data sets.

When it comes to solving complicated real-world problems, such as those involving weakly-supervised, multi-task, and multi-modal learning paradigms, He et al. [3] go into great detail. New methods for enhancing the performance and interpretation of transformer networks are also covered in this article, along with comparisons to convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The standard input for image processing is a three-dimensional bitmap with a grid of voxels, which are three-dimensional pixels. In contrast to MRI, which is based on the strength of signals from proton particles both during relaxation and after applying extremely strong magnetic fields, CT scan greyscale intensity is dependent on X-ray absorption. The purpose of this article is to raise knowledge about transformers and their use in medical image processing by providing a primer and a position paper. To be more precise, we start by outlining the fundamental ideas of the attention process that is inherent to transformers and other fundamental parts. Methods that are considered advanced, such as weakly-supervised learning and model modification, are hardly used. Because of the limited amount of time available during surgery, the resolution of the real-time intraoperative imaging is decreased compared to the pre-operative images. In addition, the patient's lower-resolution intra-operative anatomy cannot be reliably compared to the high-resolution pre-operative imaging due to the geometric deformations that typically occur during surgery. Using image registration, surgeons are able to establish a relationship between the two image sets. Finally, studies involving medical image analysis are still very important. There has been no satisfactory resolution to any of the aforementioned issues, and these flaws can yet be improved upon.

According to Sarkar and Li [4], the best way to boost contrast is by histogram equalisation. Authors suggested "modified histogram-based contrast enhancement utilising homomorphic filtering" as a possible name (mhfil). There were two phases to the handling procedure. The initial step was enhancing global contrast through histogram adjustment. In addition, picture sharpening makes use of the planned second phase of homomorphic filtering. A number of domains have made use of deep learning techniques, including computer vision, medical

diagnosis and prognosis, and natural language processing. In computer vision, it has grown into a significant area of study. Thanks to advancements in deep learning, medical imaging is now a massive and critically essential field of study. These deep learning algorithms have the potential to detect and diagnose diseases, prevent illness outbreaks, and reduce operational costs for both patients and hospital administration. An effective method to boost the picture segmentation model's efficiency is still needed. Thus, various new deep learning model architectures can be investigated by future researchers. Research into medical picture segmentation-supported deep learning has not been without its challenges, despite the field's recent impressive accomplishments in this area. Inaccurate segmentation results fall short of meeting real-world healthcare needs.

According to Hu et al. [5], medical image analysis helps doctors analyse lesions or other anatomical structures quantitatively and qualitatively, which improves the diagnostic and prognostic reliability and accuracy. We covered the fundamentals and most used models of reinforcement learning in this article. We next investigated how medical image analysis might make use of RL models. While supervised and unsupervised learning models have seen massive deployments, medical image analysis has seen very few attempts to employ reinforcement learning. When it comes to medical picture analysis, RL approaches can often outperform human supervisors and offer fresh insights. Although reinforcement learning has been gaining traction in the field of medical analysis, many academics still struggle to comprehend and implement it in clinical settings. A contributing factor is the dearth of high-quality review articles written for experts in the field of computer science. Anatomical structure extraction for quantitative shape analysis or visualisation is known as segmentation. In a perfect clinical setting, segmentation would be quick, simple, strong against picture artefacts, and fully automated. Creating a visual representation with structure from raw, unstructured data is the end goal of segmentation. Registration completes the picture by attempting to merge photos of the same area taken using different modalities (e.g., MRI and CT) or by inserting correspondent images of the same patient taken at different periods or from separate patients. For instance, photographs are taken both before (pre-operative) and during (intra-operative) surgical procedures.

In 1895, a German physics professor named Wilhelm Rontgen invented the X-ray, which sparked the idea of medical imaging. Ionizing and nonionizing radiation are both used in medical imaging systems. For better management of medical image storage and distribution, medical imaging centres and doctors can use Proton packs, a picture archiving and communication system solution. Scanning and processing are aided by X-rays, computed tomography (CT), positron emission tomography (PET), ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and mammography. In several algorithms, interpolation plays a significant role, including those dealing with picture registration and ct data reconstruction. These methods worked best when applied sooner. Visual data analysis is still a need in the modern day, but it will require additional study in areas like machine learning to acquire.

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Figure 1: Medical Image processing architecture diagram [6]

The blueprint for the paper's medical imaging processing system is shown in Figure 1. The medical photos were initially retrieved from a database that contained three-dimensional scans of the human body taken using CT and MRI machines. System control, diagnostics, and component-to-operation system interaction are the fundamental tasks of the system supervisor module, which receives the data and processes it [52-61]. A database management system and knowledge-based subsystem module, taught using machine learning algorithms, stores the processed image and uses it to support intelligent judgments. These have already been pre-processed to get rid of any extraneous information or background noise. Afterwards, a model classification step is employed by extracting images segmented with similar attributes and features. Examples that the Classifier is not familiar with are used to test its performance. Next, the image is analysed and the diagnosis is justified during the interpretation process [62-69].

Figure 2: Use case diagram [7]

The use case diagram for the paper is shown in Figure 2. The medical images' features are gathered and processed using pre-processing procedures before being inputted into the model. By applying various classification methods, the model is able to categorise the medical photos [70-76]. After that, the illnesses are identified. Data gathering and instruction utilising algorithms for machine learning. Gathering the necessary data sets is the first step in building the medical image processing model. Based on medical picture databases, the data set applies a training algorithm [77-83].

One possible placement for the pre-processing segment is just before the data coaching and testing phases. The x-ray is a diagnostic instrument that is used rather often in the medical industry. During the picture pre-processing step, digital image processing software apply several approaches to the input images [84-91]. Since the selected input photographs will include a variety of sounds and undesirable information, the raw images acquired from the hospitals will

not be suitable for direct processing. As a result, processing the input photos beforehand is necessary for analysis. All medical imaging applications, including segmentation and classification, require image pre-processing before proceeding with processing (Figure 3) [92-99].

Figure 3: Pre-processing of data [8]

The process of segmentation involves dividing a picture into smaller areas that share characteristics including colour, texture, contrast, brightness, and grayscale level. Part of what segmentation does is break down images into their component objects [100-109]. Understanding the structure of the body, pinpointing specific areas of interest, and detecting abnormalities like tumours and lesions are all goals of medical image segmentation. We have finished classifying segmentation strategies based on grey-level-based and textural feature techniques from the perspective of medical image processing. The data is then divided into two sets, training data and testing data, with the former making up 70% and the latter 30% respectively after the pre-processing phase [110-117].

In order to evaluate photos, feature extraction first identifies a region of interest (ROI). It entails transforming the picture from its basic pixel data into more abstract forms. We can glean valuable insights from these more abstract depictions. Finding the optimal feature extraction strategy for medical image classification is the goal of this effort. This study takes into account the most important feature extraction approaches for medical pictures, including local binary patterns (LBP), gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLC M), completed local binary patterns (clbp), and local tetra patterns (LTRP) [118-121]. To make sure the model can be accurately anticipated, testing it is essential. Forecasting on the test set is the initial stage. classification is a two-part supervised learning approach that consists of training and testing. The classifier learns from a training set, which is a collection of samples used throughout the training phase. When a classifier is in testing, it is put to the test on samples it is unfamiliar with. Artificial intelligence techniques known as knowledge-based systems operate inside specific domains to provide rationale for smart decisions [122-128]. Acquiring and representing knowledge makes use of a wide range of knowledge representation strategies, frameworks, scripts, and rules. The most fundamental benefits of this kind of system include the following: knowledge documentation; intelligent decision assistance; self-learning; reasoning; and explanation. A confusion matrix is used to visualise the classifier-based dataset prediction. It computes the four parameters tp, tn, fp, and fn, as well as the accuracy metrics.

Assuming someone else's medical records is possible with a number of techniques. Applying machine learning techniques to a dataset—in this case, photographs of tumors—and contextual information about the dataset (in our example, benign or malignant tumors). Following this, the algorithm can use the training data to refine its prediction abilities (in our example, whether a different image depicts benign or malignant tumour tissue). When the algorithm system learns to optimise its parameters and improve performance, it increases the number of test instances that are diagnosed correctly. During training, the system of machine learning algorithms compares the labels provided with a collection of input photographs to determine which image attributes, when applied, would lead to the accurate categorization of the image, i.e., whether it depicts a

benign or malignant tumour. (b) After the system has mastered image classification, it applies the learnt model to fresh images in order to aid radiologists in determining the type of tumour. This allows for prediction.

Results and Discussions

Using a dataset of input photographs and machine learning techniques, this work proposes a medical image processing system that can correctly categorise images as either showing the early stages of a medical illness or its progression. Next, the system of machine learning algorithms determines which image feature combinations work best for image classification or metric computation in the specified picture region. There are a variety of approaches, and they all have their advantages and disadvantages. The majority of these machine learning techniques have open-source counterparts, which makes them accessible for experimentation with photos.

When it comes to processing images, machine learning algorithms work wonders. Machine learning (ML) segmentation and classification approaches were categorised as either supervised or unsupervised in this study. Some examples of supervised machine learning algorithms include k-nearest neighbours (K-NN), decision trees (DT), regression (linear and logistic), random forest (rf), artificial neural networks (ANN), gradient boosting, and naïve Bayes models. These algorithms create mathematical models with the help of a set of labelled images that are used for training. In unsupervised learning, the output labels are not necessary for the mathematical models that are created. Algorithms sort data according to patterns they find. Principal component analysis (PCA), fuzzy c-means, apriori algorithm, k-means clustering, hierarchical clustering, and other similar unsupervised machine learning techniques (FCM).

The current setup is based on a number of mechanical algorithms that are employed by CT and MRI scanners to help with disease diagnosis, medical intervention guidance (such as surgical planning), and research. Meanwhile, the suggested method uses deep learning and machine learning algorithms to examine the test data set and draw conclusions about the problem from the patterns found in the model.

Segmentation, classification, and abnormality detection are just a few of the aspects that can be included in the final product of medical image processing that is based on machine learning. As illustrated above, medical images can be useful for diagnosing cancers and other anomalies when image segmentation techniques are used to isolate certain organs or tissues.

Machine learning in medical image processing makes use of a wide variety of algorithms and methods for analysing and making sense of medical pictures. Healthcare providers can greatly benefit from the output results of these procedures when it comes to patient monitoring, therapy planning, and diagnosis. It is possible to distinguish between normal and abnormal tissues or organs using classification systems.

An important metric for evaluating the efficacy of machine learning algorithms in medical image processing is the precision of the result graphs produced by the algorithms. The output result's accuracy is defined as the degree to which it corresponds to the ground truth or the real medical condition diagnosis. There are a number of ways to measure the precision of medical image processing's output result graphs, including sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and negative predictive value (NPV). In this case, we apply sensitive techniques and account for epoch and recall variables in our accuracy graph.

Conclusion and Future Enhancements

For the purpose of medical condition prediction utilising machine learning algorithms, this paper proposed hybrid techniques. Training and testing, along with feature selection and calculation, are the main processes involved in creating this paper. Feature extraction is the initial stage of machine learning since it contains the decision-making information. Factors like ground-glass texture, which can be difficult to quantify, are examples of those that can be difficult to compute or portray. It is important for image characteristics to be resistant to changes in noise, intensity,

and rotation angles while dealing with medical imaging data. While it is feasible to derive numerous features from an image, doing so with an excessive number of features could result in overfitting instead than uncovering the actual reasoning behind a decision. Feature selection is the process of deciding which features to employ in order to get the most accurate forecasts. One way to choose characteristics is to see if there are any correlations between them. If there are a lot of associated features, it's likely that there are some features, and you may delete some of them without losing any information. Having insufficient instances makes it impossible for a machine or human to identify the characteristics that differentiate one object class from another. How different the classes are will have a significant impact on the precise amount of examples needed for each class. When working with a small dataset, one common approach is to employ the cross-validation technique to gauge the performance of a machine learning system. To use cross-validation, one must first choose some instances to train with and then label others as test cases. Testing of the learnt state follows training. The procedure is then carried out again, but this time a new subset of the training samples is used for testing purposes. Extreme scenarios can be addressed with leave-one-out cross-validation, which entails using all of the examples for training and removing just one for testing.

Future Enhancements

While there are certain limits, hybrid approaches to medical condition prediction employing machine learning have achieved remarkable diagnoses of numerous diseases. Machine learning used to be more dependent on structured input, and many methods might fail to train with even a single missing data point. Machine learning has recently had a renaissance because to new algorithms and massive improvements in computing power and data. To make the best predictions about classes using the characteristics of the training samples, the procedure followed to build the model will be utilised. In certain cases, "real-world" testing makes use of a third group of instances. You can have more faith that the algorithm will produce accurate results in real life if it does well on a "unseen" test set. Image processing with machine learning algorithms has come a long way, but there are still a lot of caveats that need to be addressed. In the selected area, much more work remains to be accomplished.

References

1. Y. Mohamed Y. Abdallah and T. Alqahtani, "Research in medical imaging using image processing techniques," in *Medical Imaging - Principles and Applications [Working Title]*, IntechOpen, 2019.
2. M. Puttagunta and S. Ravi, "Medical image analysis based on deep learning approach," *Multimed. Tools Appl.*, vol. 80, no. 16, pp. 24365–24398, 2021.
3. K. He et al., "Transformers in Medical Image Analysis: A Review," *arXiv [cs.CV]*, 2022.
4. K. Sarkar and B. Li, "Deep learning for medical image segmentation," in *Research Anthology on Improving Medical Imaging Techniques for Analysis and Intervention*, IGI Global, 2022, pp. 861–891.
5. M. Hu, J. Zhang, L. Matkovic, T. Liu, and X. Yang, "Reinforcement learning in medical image analysis: Concepts, applications, challenges, and future directions," *arXiv [cs.CV]*, 2022.
6. R. Mironov and R. Kountchev, "Architecture for Medical Image Processing," in *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, Heidelberg: Springer International Publishing, 2013, pp. 225–234.
7. Marija Blagojević, Maja Radovic, Marjan Milosevic, "Modeling and implementation of medical information systems: Use case 'medical examination appointments,'" *Metalurgia International*, vol. 16, pp. 202-205, 2012.

8. O. Ariyo, Q. Zhi-guang, and L. Tian, "Fusion of Gaussian mixture model and spatial fuzzy C-means for brain MR image segmentation," *DEStech Trans. Comput. Sci. Eng.*, no. csae, 2018.
9. R. Boina, "Assessing the Increasing Rate of Parkinson's Disease in the US and its Prevention Techniques," *International Journal of Biotechnology Research and Development*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–18, 2022.
10. I. Khalifa, H. Abd Al-glil, and M. M. Abbassy, "Mobile hospitalization," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 80, no. 13, pp. 18–23, 2013.
11. I. Khalifa, H. Abd Al-glil, and M. M. Abbassy, "Mobile hospitalization for Kidney Transplantation," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 92, no. 6, pp. 25–29, 2014.
12. M. M. Abbassy and A. Abo-Alnadr, "Rule-based emotion AI in Arabic Customer Review," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 10, no. 9, 2019.
13. M. M. Abbassy and W. M. Ead, "Intelligent Greenhouse Management System," 2020 6th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS), 2020.
14. M. M. Abbassy, "Opinion mining for Arabic customer feedback using machine learning," *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, vol. 12, no. SP3, pp. 209–217, 2020.
15. M. M. Abbassy, "The human brain signal detection of Health Information System IN EDSAC: A novel cipher text attribute based encryption with EDSAC distributed storage access control," *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, vol. 12, no. SP7, pp. 858–868, 2020.
16. M. M. and S. Mesbah, "Effective e-government and citizens adoption in Egypt," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 133, no. 7, pp. 7–13, 2016.
17. M.M.Abbassy, A.A. Mohamed "Mobile Expert System to Detect Liver Disease Kind", *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 320–324, 2016.
18. R. A. Sadek, D. M. Abd-alazeem, and M. M. Abbassy, "A new energy-efficient multi-hop routing protocol for heterogeneous wireless sensor networks," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 11, 2021.
19. S. Derindere Köseoğlu, W. M. Ead, and M. M. Abbassy, "Basics of Financial Data Analytics," *Financial Data Analytics*, pp. 23–57, 2022.
20. W. Ead and M. Abbassy, "Intelligent Systems of Machine Learning Approaches for developing E-services portals," *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Energy Web*, p. 167292, 2018.
21. W. M. Ead and M. M. Abbassy, "A general cyber hygiene approach for financial analytical environment," *Financial Data Analytics*, pp. 369–384, 2022.
22. W. M. Ead and M. M. Abbassy, "IoT based on plant diseases detection and classification," 2021 7th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS), 2021.
23. W. M. Ead, M. M. Abbassy, and E. El-Abd, "A general framework information loss of utility-based anonymization in Data Publishing," *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, vol. 12, no. 5, pp. 1450–1456, 2021.

24. A. M. El-Kady, M. M. Abbassy, H. H. Ali, and M. F. Ali, "Advancing Diabetic Foot Ulcer Detection Based On Resnet And Gan Integration," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, vol. 102, no. 6, pp. 2258–2268, 2024.
25. M. M. Abbassy and W. M. Ead, "Fog computing-based public e-service application in service-oriented architecture," *International Journal of Cloud Computing*, vol. 12, no. 2–4, pp. 163–177, 2023.
26. AbdulKader, H., ElAbd, E., & Ead, W. (2016). Protecting Online Social Networks Profiles by Hiding Sensitive Data Attributes. *Procedia Computer Science*, 82, 20–27.
27. Fattoh, I. E., Kamal Alsheref, F., Ead, W. M., & Youssef, A. M. (2022). Semantic sentiment classification for covid-19 tweets using universal sentence encoder. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022, 1–8.
28. Ead, W. M., Abdel-Wahed, W. F., & Abdul-Kader, H. (2013). Adaptive Fuzzy Classification-Rule Algorithm In Detection Malicious Web Sites From Suspicious URLs. *Int. Arab. J. E Technol.*, 3, 1–9.
29. Abdelazim, M. A., Nasr, M. M., & Ead, W. M. (2020). A survey on classification analysis for cancer genomics: Limitations and novel opportunity in the era of cancer classification and Target Therapies. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Public Health*, 23(24).
30. Alsheref, F. K., Fattoh, I. E., & M.Ead, W. (2022). Automated prediction of employee attrition using ensemble model based on machine learning algorithms. *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, 2022, 1–9.
31. Srinath Venkatesan, "Design an Intrusion Detection System based on Feature Selection Using ML Algorithms", *MSEA*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 702–710, Feb. 2023
32. Srinath Venkatesan, "Identification Protocol Heterogeneous Systems in Cloud Computing", *MSEA*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 615–621, Feb. 2023.
33. Cristian Laverde Albarraçín, Srinath Venkatesan, Arnaldo Yana Torres, Patricio Yáñez-Moreta, Juan Carlos Juarez Vargas, "Exploration on Cloud Computing Techniques and Its Energy Concern", *MSEA*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 749–758, Feb. 2023.
34. Srinath Venkatesan, "Perspectives and Challenges of Artificial Intelligence Techniques in Commercial Social Networks" Volume 21, No 5 (2023).
35. Srinath Venkatesan, Zubaida Rehman, "The Power Of 5g Networks and Emerging Technology and Innovation: Overcoming Ongoing Century Challenges" *Ion exchange and adsorption*, Volume 23, Issue 1, 2023.
36. Srinath Venkatesan, "Challenges of Datafication: Theoretical, Training, And Communication Aspects of Artificial Intelligence" *Ion exchange and adsorption*. Volume 23, Issue 1, 2023.
37. Giovanni Haro-Sosa , Srinath Venkatesan, "Personified Health Care Transitions With Automated Doctor Appointment System: Logistics", *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, pp. 2832–2839, Feb. 2023
38. Srinath Venkatesan, Sandeep Bhatnagar, José Luis Tinajero León, "A Recommender System Based on Matrix Factorization Techniques Using Collaborative Filtering Algorithm", *neuroquantology*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 864-872, march 2023.
39. Srinath Venkatesan, "Utilization of Media Skills and Technology Use Among Students and Educators in The State of New York", *Neuroquantology*, Vol. 21, No 5, pp. 111-124, (2023).

40. Srinath Venkatesan, Sandeep Bhatnagar, Iván Mesias Hidalgo Cajo, Xavier Leopoldo Gracia Cervantes, "Efficient Public Key Cryptosystem for wireless Network", *Neuroquantology*, Vol. 21, No 5, pp. 600-606, (2023).
41. E. Vashishtha and H. Kapoor, "Enhancing patient experience by automating and transforming free text into actionable consumer insights: a natural language processing (NLP) approach," *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 275-288, Oct. 2023.
42. K. Shukla, E. Vashishtha, M. Sandhu, and R. Choubey, "Natural Language Processing: Unlocking the Power of Text and Speech Data," Xoffencer International Book Publication House, 2023, p. 251.
43. Kaur, L., & Shah, S. (2022). Production of bacterial cellulose by *Acetobacter tropicalis* isolated from decaying apple waste. *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, 34(2), 453–458.
44. Kaur, L., & Shah, S. (2022). Screening and characterization of cellulose-producing bacterial strains from decaying fruit waste. *International Journal of Food and Nutritional Science*, 11 (1), 8–14.
45. Verma,S & Kaur,L. . (2018). Identification Of Waste Utilizing Bacteria From Fruit Waste. *Global Journal for Research Analysis Volume-7(6, June)*
46. Kaur, L., & Singh, N., (2000) Effect of mustard oil and process variables extrusion behavior of rice grits. *Journal Of Food Science And Technology*. Mysore, 37, 656–660.
47. Thapar, Lakhvinder. (2017). Bulk And Nano-Zinc Oxide Particles Affecting Physio-Morphological Properties Of *Pisum Sativum*. *International Journal Of Research In Engineering And Applied Sciences (IJREAS)*.
48. Sneha, M., Thapar, L. (2019). Estimation of Protein Intake on the Basis of Urinary Urea Nitrogen in Patients with Non-Alcoholic Fatty Liver. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 7, 2321–9653.
49. Thapar, Lakhvinder. (2017). Fermentation Potential Of Prebiotic Juice Obtained From Natural Sources. *International Journal Of Advanced Research*. 5. 1779-1785.
50. Mittal, Srishty & Thapar, Lakhvinder. (2019). Vitamin D Levels Between The Tuberculosis Infected And Non – Infected Subjects In 16-25 Years Of Age.
51. S Silvia Priscila, M Hemalatha, “ Diagnosisof heart disease with particle bee-neural network” *Biomedical Research, Special Issue*, pp. S40-S46, 2018.
52. Priscila, S.S., & Hemalatha, H. (2018). Heart disease prediction using integer-coded genetic algorithm (ICGA) based particle clonal neural network (ICGA-PCNN). *Bonfring International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Science*, 8(2), 15–19.
53. S. Silvia Priscila. and H. Hemalatha, “Improving the performance of entropy ensembles of neural networks (EENNS) on classification of heart disease prediction”,” *Int J Pure Appl Math*, vol. 117, no. 7, pp. 371–386, 2017.
54. Razeghi, M., Dehzangi, A., Wu, D., McClintock, R., Zhang, Y., Durlin, Q., ... & Meng, F. (2019, May). Antimonite-based gap-engineered type-II superlattice materials grown by MBE and MOCVD for the third generation of infrared imagers. In *Infrared Technology and Applications XLV* (Vol. 11002, pp. 108-125). SPIE.
55. Meng, F., Zhang, L., & Chen, Y. (2023) FEDEMB: An Efficient Vertical and Hybrid Federated Learning Algorithm Using Partial Network Embedding.
56. Meng, F., Jagadeesan, L., & Thottan, M. (2021). Model-based reinforcement learning for service mesh fault resiliency in a web application-level. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.13621*.

57. Meng, F., Zhang, L., Chen, Y., & Wang, Y. (2023). Sample-based Dynamic Hierarchical Transformer with Layer and Head Flexibility via Contextual Bandit. Authorea Preprints.
58. S. S. Banait, S. S. Sane, D. D. Bage and A. R. Ugale, "Reinforcement mSVM: An Efficient Clustering and Classification Approach using reinforcement and supervised Technique," *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering (IJISAE)*, Vol.35, no.1S, p .78-89. 2022.
59. S. S. Banait, S. S. Sane and S. A. Talekar, "An efficient Clustering Technique for Big Data Mining" , *International Journal of Next Generation Computing (IJNGC)* , Vol.13, no.3, pp.702-717. 2022.
60. Veena, A., Gowrishankar, S. An automated pre-term prediction system using EHG signal with the aid of deep learning technique. *Multimed Tools Appl* (2023).
61. A. Veena and S. Gowrishankar, "Context based healthcare informatics system to detect gallstones using deep learning methods," *International Journal of Advanced Technology and Engineering Exploration*, vol. 9, (96), pp. 1661-1677, 2022.
62. Veena, A., Gowrishankar, S. (2021). Healthcare Analytics: Overcoming the Barriers to Health Information Using Machine Learning Algorithms. In: Chen, J.IZ., Tavares, J.M.R.S., Shakya, S., Iliyasa, A.M. (eds) *Image Processing and Capsule Networks. ICIPCN 2020. Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol 1200. Springer, Cham.
63. A. Veena and S. Gowrishankar, "Processing of Healthcare Data to Investigate the Correlations and the Anomalies," 2020 Fourth International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC), Palladam, India, 2020, pp. 611-617,
64. A. Veena and S. Gowrishankar, "Applications, Opportunities, and Current Challenges in the Healthcare Industry", 2022 Healthcare 4.0: Health Informatics and Precision Data Management, 2022, pp. 27–50.
65. Naeem, A. B., Senapati, B., Islam Sudman, M. S., Bashir, K., & Ahmed, A. E. M. (2023). Intelligent road management system for autonomous, non-autonomous, and VIP vehicles. *World Electric Veh. J*, 14(9).
66. A. M. Soomro et al., "Constructor development: Predicting object communication errors," in 2023 IEEE International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering, Sciences and Technology (ICES&T), 2023.
67. A. M. Soomro et al., "In MANET: An improved hybrid routing approach for disaster management," in 2023 IEEE International Conference on Emerging Trends in Engineering, Sciences and Technology (ICES&T), 2023.
68. B. Senapati and B. S. Rawal, "Adopting a deep learning split-protocol based predictive maintenance management system for industrial manufacturing operations," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023, pp. 22–39.
69. Biswaranjan Senapati, B., Rawal, B.S. (2023). Adopting a Deep Learning Split-Protocol Based Predictive Maintenance Management System for Industrial Manufacturing Operations. In: Hsu, CH., Xu, M., Cao, H., Baghban, H., Shawkat Ali, A.B.M. (eds) *Big Data Intelligence and Computing. DataCom 2022. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 13864. Springer, Singapore.
70. Sabugaa, M., Senapati, B., Kupriyanov, Y., Danilova, Y., Irgasheva, S., Potekhina, E. (2023). Evaluation of the Prognostic Significance and Accuracy of Screening Tests for Alcohol Dependence Based on the Results of Building a Multilayer Perceptron. In: Silhavy, R., Silhavy, P. (eds) *Artificial Intelligence Application in Networks and Systems. CSOC 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 724. Springer, Cham.

71. Senapati, B., & Rawal, B. S. (2023). Quantum communication with RLP quantum resistant cryptography in industrial manufacturing. *Cyber Security and Applications*, 100019, 100019.
72. K. Peddireddy, "Effective Usage of Machine Learning in Aero Engine test data using IoT based data driven predictive analysis," *Nternational J. Adv. Res. Comput. Commun. Eng.*, vol. 12, no. 10, 2023.
73. K. Peddireddy and D. Banga, "Enhancing Customer Experience through Kafka Data Steams for Driven Machine Learning for Complaint Management," *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, vol. 71, pp. 7–13, 2023.
74. A. Peddireddy and K. Peddireddy, "Next-Gen CRM Sales and Lead Generation with AI," *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology*, vol. 71, no. 3, pp. 21–26, 2023.
75. K. Peddireddy, "Kafka-based Architecture in Building Data Lakes for Real-time Data Streams," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, vol. 185, no. 9, pp. 1–3, 2023.
76. K. Peddireddy, "Streamlining enterprise data processing, reporting and realtime alerting using Apache Kafka," in *2023 11th International Symposium on Digital Forensics and Security (ISDFS)*, 2023.
77. Mohd Akbar, Irshad Ahmad, Mohsina Mirza, Manavver Ali, Praveen Barmavatu "Enhanced authentication for de-duplication of big data on cloud storage system using machine learning approach", *Cluster Computing*, Springer Publisher, 2023.
78. Mohd Akbar, Mohammed Mujtaba Waseem, Syeda Husna Mehanoor, Praveen Barmavatu, "Blockchain-based cyber-security trust model with multi-risk protection scheme for secure data transmission in cloud computing", *Cluster Computing*, Springer Publisher, 2024.
79. J Immanuel Durai Raj, RB Durairaj, S Vijay Ananth, Praveen Barmavatu "Experimental investigation of the effect of e-waste fillers on the mechanical properties of Kenaf woven fiber composites" *Environmental Quality Management*, Wiley Publishers, 2024.
80. Prathiba Rex, Mohammed Kalil Rahiman, Praveen Barmavatu, Sai Bharadwaj Aryasomayajula Venkata Satya Lakshm, Nagaraj Meenakshisundaram "Catalytic pyrolysis of polypropylene and polyethylene terephthalate waste using graphene oxide-sulfonated zirconia (GO-Szr) and analysis of its oil properties for Bharat Stage VI fuel production", *Environmental Quality Management*, Wiley Publishers, Vol -33/issue-1/pp: 1-11, 2023.
81. A. Latha, R. Ganesan, A. V. S. L. Sai Bharadwaj, Praveen Barmavatu "An experimental investigation of textile dyeing wastewater using modified electro Fenton processwith optimization by response surface methodology", *Environmental Quality Management*, Wiley Publishers, 2023.
82. Jebasingh Immanuel Durai Raj, Ramamoorthy Iyer Balasubramaniyan Durairaj, Amaladas John Rajan, Praveen Barmavatu "Effect of e-waste nanofillers on the mechanical, thermal, and wear properties of epoxy-blend sisal woven fiber-reinforced composites" *Green Processing and Synthesis*, De Gruyter Publisher, Vol-12/issue-1, 20230164, 2023.
83. Sandeep Ohol, Mathew V K, Virendra Bhojwani, Naveen G Patil, Praveen Barmavatu "Effect of PCM filled Hollow Fin heat sink for Cooling of Electronic Components - A Numerical Approach for thermal management prospective" *International Journal of Modern Physics C*, World Scientific Publisher, 2024.
84. Kumaravel Subramanian, Nagaraj Meenakshisundaram, Praveen Barmavatu, "Experimental and theoretical investigation to optimize the performance of solar still", *Desalination and Water Treatment*, Volume 318, 100343 April 2024.
85. Kumaravel Subramanian, Nagaraj Meenakshisundaram, Praveen Barmavatu, Bharathiraja Govindarajan, "Experimental investigation on the effect of nano-enhanced phase change

- materials on the thermal performance of single slope solar still”, *Desalination and Water Treatment*, Volume 319, 100416 July 2024.
86. Prathiba Rex, Nagaraj Meenakshisundaram, Praveen Barmavatu, “Sustainable valorisation of kitchen waste through greenhouse solar drying and microwave pyrolysis– technology readiness level for the production of biochar”, *Journal of Environmental Health Science and Engineering*, 2024.
 87. Yalagandala akshay kumar, Shaik shafee, Barmavatu Praveen “Experimental investigation of residual stresses in a die casted alluminium fly wheel” *Elsevier material today proceedings* ISSN 2214-7853/vol19/issue-Part-02/pp: A10-A18/October2019.
 88. T. Prasad, Barmavatu Praveen, Yalagandala Akshay Kumar, Kunchala Krishna, “Development of carbon & glass fiber reinforced composites with the addition of nano egg-shell powder”, *Springer Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering (LNME)*, ICIME 2021, ISBN 978-981-16-7282-8 pp: 569-577.
 89. Barmavatu Praveen, Madan mohan reddy Nune, Yalagandala akshay kumar, Rathod Subhash, “Investigating the Effect of Minimum Quantity Lubrication on Surface Finish of EN 47 Steel Material”, *Elsevier material today proceedings*, ISSN 2214-7853, Vol-38/Part-05, pp-32-53-3257,
 90. Barmavatu Praveen, Yalagandala Akshay Kumar, Banoth Sravanthi, H. Ameresh “Methodological Investigation on recycling of Plastic Polymers-A Review” *International journal of scientific & technological research* Vol-9/issue-03/pp:1537-1542/march 2020.
 91. Barmavatu Praveen & S Chakradhara Goud “CFD approach for different fluids varients in compact heat exchanger at different parametric conditions” *International journal of scientific & technological research* Vol-8/issue-12/pp:2288-2296/december2019.
 92. Barmavatu Praveen & S Chakradhara Goud “fabrication of compact heat exchanger with composite alloys” *International journal of innovative technology and exploring engineering* Vol-8/issue-6s4/pp:717-721/April 2019.
 93. Soham Das, Ranjan Kumar Ghadai, Gaurav Sapkota, Spandan Guha, Praveen Barmavatu, Kottala Ravi Kumar “Optimization of CNC turning parameters of copper–nickel (Cu–Ni) alloy using VIKOR, MOORA and GRA techniques” *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, Springer Publisher, 2024.
 94. U.B. Vishwanatha, Y. Dharmendar Reddy, Praveen Barmavatu, B. Shankar Goud “Insights into stretching ratio and velocity slip on MHD rotating flow of Maxwell nanofluid over a stretching sheet: Semi-analytical technique OHAM”, *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*, Elsevier Publishers, Vol-100/issue-3/pp: 100937-10, 2023.
 95. Ganesh Botla, Praveen Barmavatu, Michael Pohorely, Michal Jeremias, Vineet Singh Sikarwar “Optimization of value-added products using response surface methodology from the HDPE waste plastic by thermal cracking”. *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress*, Elsevier Publishers, Vol-50, 102514, May 2024.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S245190492400132X>
 96. Shaheen Sultana, P Pandian, Jeetendra Kumar Gupta, B Rajkamal, Praveen Barmavatu, Dibyalochan Mohanty “Hybrids of imidazole with indoline derivatives: Microwave assisted synthesis, molecular docking studies, possible biological activities”. *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society*, Elsevier Publishers, Vol-101/issue-4/pp: 101143-10, 2024.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019452224000232>
 97. H. Rafi, H. Rafiq, and M. Farhan, “Antagonization of monoamine reuptake transporters by agmatine improves anxiolytic and locomotive behaviors commensurate with fluoxetine and methylphenidate,” *Beni-Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, pp. 1–14, 2021.

98. M. Farhan, H. Rafi, and H. Rafiq, "Dapoxetine treatment leads to attenuation of chronic unpredictable stress induced behavioral deficits in rats model of depression," *Journal of Pharmacy and Nutrition Sciences*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 222–228, 2015.
99. H. Rafi and M. Farhan, "Dapoxetine: An Innovative Approach in Therapeutic Management in Animal Model of Depression," *Pakistan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 15–22, 2015.
100. H. Rafiq, M. Farhan, H. Rafiq, S. Rehman, M. Arshad, S. Shakeel, "Inhibition of drug induced parkinsonism by chronic supplementation of quercetin in haloperidol-treated wistars," *Pakistan journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, vol. 6, no. 35, pp. 1655-1622, 2023. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36789825>.
101. R S Gaayathri, S. S. Rajest, V. K. Nomula, R. Regin, "Bud-D: Enabling Bidirectional Communication with ChatGPT by adding Listening and Speaking Capabilities," *FMDB Transactions on Sustainable Computer Letters.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 49–63, 2023.
102. V. K. Nomula, R. Steffi, and T. Shynu, "Examining the Far-Reaching Consequences of Advancing Trends in Electrical, Electronics, and Communications Technologies in Diverse Sectors," *FMDB Transactions on Sustainable Energy Sequence*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 27–37, 2023.
103. P. S. Venkateswaran, F. T. M. Ayasrah, V. K. Nomula, P. Paramasivan, P. Anand, and K. Bogeshwaran, "Applications of artificial intelligence tools in higher education," in *Advances in Business Information Systems and Analytics*, IGI Global, USA, pp. 124–136, 2023.
104. R. C. A. Komperla, K. S. Pokkuluri, V. K. Nomula, G. U. Gowri, S. S. Rajest, and J. Rahila, "Revolutionizing biometrics with AI-enhanced X-ray and MRI analysis," in *Advances in Medical Technologies and Clinical Practice*, IGI Global, 2024, pp. 1–16.
105. S. S. S. Ramesh, A. Jose, P. R. Samraysh, H. Mulabagala, M. S. Minu, and V. K. Nomula, "Domain generalization and multidimensional approach for brain MRI segmentation using contrastive representation transfer learning algorithm," in *Advances in Medical Technologies and Clinical Practice*, IGI Global, 2024, pp. 17–33.
106. E. Geo Francis and S. Sheeja, "An optimized intrusion detection model for wireless sensor networks based on MLP-CatBoost algorithm," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 2024.
107. E. Geo Francis and S. Sheeja, "SHAKE-ESDRL-based energy efficient intrusion detection and hashing system," *Annals of Telecommunications*, 2023.
108. E. Geo Francis and S. Sheeja, "Intrusion detection system and mitigation of threats in IoT networks using AI techniques: A review," *Engineering and Applied Science Research*, 2023, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 633–645.
109. E. Geo Francis and S. Sheeja, "A Novel RDAE Based PSR-QKD Framework for Energy Efficient Intrusion Detection," 2022 International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Communication Systems (ICKES), Chickballapur, India, 2022, pp. 1-6.
110. B. Karthikeyan, R. A. Devi, and M. Munshi, "Utilizing Deep Learning for the Classification of Brain Tumours Using MRI," *AVE Trends In Intelligent Health Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–9, 2024.
111. A. Chitra, R. Rajpriya, D. A. Karras, and N. R. B. Sridharlakshmi "An Exhaustive Study of Parasitic Organisms and Pathological Effects on Human Health," *AVE Trends In Intelligent Health Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 10 –18, 2024.
112. N. Hassoun, R. Kateeb and N. Thallaj "Effect of Ginger and Garlic Extracts on In-vitro Thrombolysis," *AVE Trends In Intelligent Health Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 19 –27, 2024.

113. U. Obeta, D. Deko, and E. Mantu “Deep Learning-Based Diagnostic Techniques for Cancer: Extensive Testing and Clinical Application Insights,” *AVE Trends In Intelligent Health Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 28 –37, 2024.
114. M. P. N. V. Kumar, A. Chitra, R. Rajpriya, B. Gayathri, C. Roberts, and S. S. Rajest “Brain-Optimized U-Net Model for Intraretinal Cystoid Fluid Segmentation in Optical Coherence Tomography,” *AVE Trends In Intelligent Health Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 38 – 50, 2024.
115. E. Geo Francis and S. Sheeja, “Towards an Optimal Security Using Multifactor Scalable Lightweight Cryptography for IoT,” 2022 3rd International Conference on Communication, Computing and Industry 4.0 (C2I4), Bangalore, India, 2022, pp. 1-6.
116. E. Geo Francis, S. Sheeja and Joseph Jismy, “A Three-layer Convolution Neural Network Approach for Intrusion Detection in IoT,” 2023 Eleventh International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Information Systems (ICICIS), Cairo, Egypt, 2023, pp. 261-268.
117. E. Geo Francis, S. Sheeja and E. F. Antony John, “IoT Intrusion Detection Using Two-Tier-Convolutional Deep-Learning Model,” 2023 International Conference on IoT, Communication and Automation Technology (ICICAT), Gorakhpur, India, 2023, pp. 1-7.
118. Reddy, A. R. P., & Ayyadapu, A. K. R. (2020). Automating Incident Response: Ai-Driven Approaches To Cloud Security Incident Management. *Chelonian Research Foundation*, 15(2), 1-10.
119. Reddy, A. R. P. (2021). Machine Learning Models for Anomaly Detection in Cloud Infrastructure Security. *NeuroQuantology*, 19(12), 755-763.
120. Reddy, A. R. P. (2021). The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Proactive Cyber Threat Detection In Cloud Environments. *NeuroQuantology*, 19(12), 764-773.
121. Reddy, A. R. P. (2022). The Future of Cloud Security: Ai-Powered Threat Intelligence and Response. *International Neurourology Journal*, 26(4), 45-52.
122. Reddy, A. R. P. (2023). Navigating the Cloud's Security Maze: AI and ML as Guides. *International Neurourology Journal*, 27(4), 1613-1620.
123. H. Rafi, H. Rafiq, R. Khan, F. Ahmad, J. Anis, M. Farhan, “Neuroethological study of ALCL3 and chronic forced swim stress induced memory and cognitive deficits in albino rats.,” *The Journal of Neurobehavioral Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 149–158, 2019.
124. M. Farhan, H. Rafi, and H. Rafiq, “Behavioral evidence of neuropsychopharmacological effect of imipramine in animal model of unpredictable stress induced depression” *International Journal of Biology and Biotechnology*, vol. 15, no. 22, pp. 213–221, 2018.
125. T. Ghulam, H. Rafi, A. Khan, K. Gul, and M. Z. Yousuf, “Impact of SARS-CoV2 Treatment on Development of Sensorineural Hearing Loss,” *Proceedings of the Pakistan Academy of Sciences: B. Life and Environmental Sciences.*, vol. S, no. 58, pp. 45–54, 2021.
126. M. Awais, A. Bhuva, D. Bhuva, S. Fatima, and T. Sadiq, “Optimized DEC: An effective cough detection framework using optimal weighted Features-aided deep Ensemble classifier for COVID-19,” *Biomed. Signal Process. Control*, p. 105026, 2023.
127. D. R. Bhuva and S. Kumar, “A novel continuous authentication method using biometrics for IOT devices,” *Internet of Things*, vol. 24, no. 100927, p. 100927, 2023.
128. D. Bhuva and S. Kumar, “Securing space cognitive communication with blockchain,” in *2023 IEEE Cognitive Communications for Aerospace Applications Workshop (CCAAW)*, 2023.